

Synthesis of Some 1,5-Benzodiazepines, Part II

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In view of the fact that heterocyclic substituents modify the properties of the parent compounds, 1,5-benzodiazepines having heterocyclic substituent at 4-position were prepared. The compounds were screened for hypo/hyper glycemia activity. IR spectra of some 1,5-benzodiazepines were also studied.

It is observed that heterocyclic substituents significantly modify the properties of the parent compounds. In this work 1,5-benzodiazepines (I) having heterocyclic substituent at 4-position were prepared for the investigation of their biological and pharmacological properties.

1,3-Diones required for the preparation of 1,5-benzodiazepines (I) were prepared by the Baker-Venkatraman transformation of the corresponding esters, which in turn were prepared by condensing *o*-hydroxy acetophenones with heterocyclic carboxylic acids and not with acid chlorides¹. 1,3-Diones were condensed with *o*-phenylene diamine in alcohol-acetic acid medium to form 1,5-benzodiazepines.

The formation of 1,5-benzodiazepines (VII) starting from *o*-hydroxyacetophenones can be represented as follows:

Melting points, % yields and results of elemental analysis of the esters, 1,3-diones and 1,5-benzodiazepines prepared for the first time are given in the following tables. The remaining compounds used in this work have been reported by the earlier workers²⁻⁵.

Infrared spectra of some of the above 1,5-benzodiazepines were studied. The spectra showed characteristic bands due to N-H stretching vibrations ($\sim 3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ ($1620\text{--}1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$), $\delta\text{N-H}$ ($1590\text{--}1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$), out of plane bending vibrations of C-H of substituted phenyls and 2-thienyl, 3-pyridyl and 4-pyridyl. A band due to $\nu\text{N-H}$ was not observed only in 2-(2'-hydroxy phenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)1,5-benzodiazepine (VII, $\text{R}_1 = \text{R}_2 = \text{R}_3 = \text{H}$, $\text{R}' = 2\text{-thienyl}$). The observation of bands due to N-H stretching vibrations indicates that 1,5-benzodiazepines can be represented by the imine structure (VIII) as well.

Similar observation was made in the earlier part of this work⁶.

TABLE 1

Srl No.	Compound (IV)			R'	M.P. °C	% Yield	Found %		Required %	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃				C	H	C	H
1.	CH ₃	H	H	2-Thienyl	55	68	64.32	4.75	64.61	4.61
2.	H	H	CH ₃	"	90	68	64.58	4.69	64.61	4.61
3.	H	H	CH ₃	3-Pyridyl	78	69	69.76	5.12	70.58	5.10
4.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	89-90	51	62.04	4.61	62.18	4.49
5.	Cl	H	H	"	80	54	60.94	3.72	60.98	3.63
6.	H	Cl	H	"	63	50	60.42	3.93	60.98	3.63
7.	H	H	Cl	"	60	56	60.68	3.74	60.98	3.63
8.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	"	86-7	60	71.09	5.36	71.37	5.57
9.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	100	58	70.66	5.64	71.37	5.57
10.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	66	64	71.38	5.55	71.37	5.57
11.	Cl	H	Cl	"	110	70	54.02	2.99	54.19	2.90
12.	H	H	Br	"	88	52	52.41	3.14	52.50	3.13
13.	BENZO	H	H	"	76	60	74.01	4.51	74.23	4.47
14.	H	CH ₃	H	4-Pyridyl	108	64	70.52	5.12	70.59	5.10
15.	CH ₃	H	H	"	93-4	56	70.86	5.03	70.59	5.10
16.	H	H	CH ₃	"	118	69	70.46	5.18	70.59	5.10
17.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	127	50	61.78	4.39	62.17	4.50
18.	Cl	H	H	"	133	63	60.32	4.25	60.98	3.63
19.	H	Cl	H	"	100	55	60.72	4.13	60.98	3.63
20.	H	H	Cl	"	104	63	60.75	3.91	60.98	3.63
21.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	"	105	70	70.55	5.49	71.30	5.57
22.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	138	71	71.34	5.65	71.37	5.57
23.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	93	64	71.10	5.71	71.39	5.57
24.	Cl	H	Cl	"	104-5	67	54.23	3.12	54.19	2.90
25.	H	H	Br	"	101	70	54.33	3.15	52.50	3.12

TABLE 2

Sr. No.	Compound V			R'	M.P. °C	% Yield	Found %		Required %	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃				C	H	C	H
1.	CH ₃	H	H	2-Thienyl	72-3	52	64.56	4.62	64.61	4.61
2.	H	CH ₃	H	"	76-7	48	64.49	4.69	64.61	4.61
3.	H	H	CH ₃	"	80	50	64.58	4.63	64.61	4.61
4.	Cl	H	H	"	97	54	55.57	3.25	55.61	3.21
5.	Cl	H	Et	"	100	58	58.21	4.24	58.24	4.21
6.	CH ₃	H	H	3-Pyridyl	154	46	70.21	5.33	70.59	5.10
7.	H	CH ₃	H	"	122	48	70.15	5.26	70.59	5.10
8.	H	H	CH ₃	"	125	47	70.32	5.25	70.59	5.10
9.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	192	65	62.01	4.55	62.17	4.50
10.	Cl	H	H	"	153	47	60.50	3.71	60.98	3.63
11.	H	Cl	H	"	163	49	60.71	3.45	60.98	3.63
12.	H	H	Cl	"	180	65	60.81	3.75	60.98	3.63
13.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	"	152	66	71.09	5.62	71.37	5.57
14.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	115	48	71.21	5.32	71.37	5.57
15.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	148	56	71.25	5.65	71.37	5.57
16.	Cl	H	Cl	"	168	49	54.01	3.12	54.19	2.99
17.	H	H	Br	"	196	56	52.18	3.21	54.50	3.12
18.	BENZO	H	H	"	165	48	73.91	4.51	74.23	4.47
19.	CH ₃	H	H	4-Pyridyl	138	50	71.51	5.25	70.59	5.10
20.	H	CH ₃	H	"	73	45	70.40	5.19	70.59	5.10
21.	H	H	CH ₃	"	123	55	70.32	5.23	70.59	5.10
22.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	168	55	62.01	4.59	62.18	4.50
23.	Cl	H	H	"	158	48	60.41	3.60	60.98	3.63
24.	H	Cl	H	"	135	47	60.72	3.81	60.98	3.63
25.	H	H	Cl	"	135	60	60.84	3.72	60.98	3.63
26.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	"	160	55	71.02	5.42	71.38	5.57
27.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	140	46	71.21	5.61	71.38	5.57
28.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	164	55	71.15	5.70	71.38	5.57
29.	Cl	H	Cl	"	115	53	53.85	3.21	54.19	2.90
30.	H	H	Br	"	118	47	52.18	3.39	52.50	3.12

TABLE 3

Sr. No.	Compound VII			R'	M.P. °C	% Yield	Found %		Required %	
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃				C	H	C	H
1.	H	H	H	2-Thienyl	206	35	71.32	4.32	71.70	4.40
2.	CH ₃	H	H	"	165	33	72.13	4.93	72.28	4.82
3.	H	CH ₃	H	"	206-7	30	72.08	4.98	72.25	4.82
4.	H	H	CH ₃	"	165	34	71.50	5.05	72.28	4.82
5.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	182-3	32	65.13	4.21	65.48	4.09
6.	Cl	H	H	"	185	30	64.52	3.72	64.68	3.69
7.	H	Cl	H	"	146	30	64.43	3.51	64.68	3.69
8.	H	H	Cl	"	176	25	64.19	3.75	64.68	3.69
9.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	"	208	30	72.53	5.31	72.83	5.20
10.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	190	36	62.63	5.37	72.83	5.20
11.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	160-2	26	72.11	5.40	72.83	5.20
12.	Cl	H	Cl	"	195	44	58.73	3.14	58.91	3.10
13.	H	H	Br	"	193	27	56.91	3.40	57.43	3.27
14.	BENZO	H	H	"	227	25	71.69	4.53	71.38	4.35
15.	Cl	H	Et	"	180	22	66.03	4.59	66.23	4.47
16.	H	H	H	3-Pyridyl	218	26	76.25	4.84	76.57	4.79
17.	CH ₃	H	H	"	208-9	30	76.91	5.30	77.06	5.20
18.	H	CH ₃	H	"	225	30	76.75	5.35	77.06	5.20
19.	H	H	CH ₃	"	184	42	76.95	5.08	77.06	5.20
20.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	203	44	69.35	4.48	69.71	4.42
21.	Cl	H	H	"	169	40	69.13	4.12	69.06	4.03
22.	H	Cl	H	"	235	25	69.01	4.12	69.06	4.03
23.	H	H	Cl	"	190	31	68.88	4.28	69.06	4.03
24.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	"	221	40	74.31	3.49	77.42	5.57
25.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	161	25	74.12	5.67	77.42	5.57
26.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	198	30	74.21	5.69	77.42	5.57
27.	Cl	H	Cl	"	193	33	62.31	3.49	62.66	3.39
28.	H	H	Br	"	202	31	60.82	3.62	61.07	3.56
29.	BENZO	H	H	"	228	32	78.79	4.77	79.12	4.67
30.	H	H	H	4-Pyridyl	191	24	76.28	4.89	76.67	4.79
31.	CH ₃	H	H	"	145	30	76.91	5.31	77.06	5.20
32.	H	CH ₃	H	"	150	34	76.84	5.03	77.06	5.20
33.	H	H	CH ₃	"	135	41	77.12	5.36	7.06	5.20
34.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	180	48	69.51	4.60	69.71	4.42
35.	Cl	H	H	"	169	23	68.75	4.15	69.06	4.03
36.	H	Cl	H	"	208	20	68.82	4.21	69.06	4.03
37.	H	H	Cl	"	192	23	69.12	3.91	69.06	4.03
38.	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	"	205	26	77.20	5.56	77.42	5.57
39.	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	"	150	20	77.35	5.71	77.42	5.57
40.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	208	22	77.21	5.62	77.42	5.57
41.	Cl	H	Cl	"	186	27	62.50	3.30	62.66	3.39
42.	H	H	Br	"	165	26	60.81	3.72	61.07	3.56

Activity of 1,5-benzodiazepines

All the compounds prepared in this work have been sent to the SK & F Laboratories, Philadelphia, U.S.A. The compounds were screened for *in vivo* hypo/hyper glycaemia activity.

Amongst the eleven compounds tested so far, only one compound that is 2-(2'-hydroxy phenyl)-4-(2-thienyl)-1,5-benzodiazepine has been found to

possess considerable hyperglycaemic action on rats.

It produced 12% increase in blood glucose content in the rat at the first hour of the test. Each compound was tested on seven rats for 4 hr. Blood samples were tested at the specific intervals. Solutions of the compounds were prepared in 5% gum tragacanth. Rats were fasted for 48 hr before the administration of the dose. Percent increase or decrease in blood glucose content effected by each compound is given in Table 4.

TABLE 4

No.	Compound VII			R'	Percentage increase (+) or decrease (-) of blood glucose effected by compound		
	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃		1st hr.	2nd hr.	4th hr.
1.	H	H	H	2-Thienyl	+12	+4	-4
2.	CH ₃	H	H	"	+2	+2	-10
3.	H	H	CH ₃	"	-3	-2	-7
4.	H	H	Br	"	+12	+5	+5
5.	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	"	+3	0	+5
6.	H	CH ₃	Cl	"	-3	-5	-5
7.	H	H	Cl	"	-2	0	-5
8.	H	Cl	H	"	-2	+2	+2
9.	H	H	H	3-Pyridyl	+3	-3	+7
10.	H	H	CH ₃	"	+7	+2	-2
11.	H	H	H	4-Pyridyl	0	-8	-15

Experimental

1. Preparation of esters (III)

Substituted *o*-hydroxy acetophenone (0.04 mol) and heterocyclic acid (0.05 mol) were dissolved in pyridine (20 ml). To this solution phosphorous oxychloride (4 ml) was added slowly with stirring, maintaining the temperature below 40°. The reaction mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 hr. The reaction mass was poured on a mixture of crushed ice (50 g) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (25 ml) (glacial acetic acid was used in case of nicotinic acid and isonicotinic acid). Usually a colourless solid separated, which was filtered, washed successively with water, 2% sodium hydroxide solution and again with water. The product obtained was crystallised from either alcohol or alcohol-water mixture. If no solid separated on pouring the reaction mixture on crushed ice and hydrochloric acid (or glacial acetic acid) the reaction mixture was extracted with ether. The ether layer was washed successively with water, 2% sodium hydroxide solution and again with water. The extract was dried with anhydrous calcium chloride and the solvent was evaporated. The viscous mass obtained was used for the B.V. transformation without further purification.

2. Preparation of 1,3-diones (IV)

A mixture of an ester, dry pyridine and powdered potassium hydroxide was stirred for about 20 min.

The reaction mixture was acidified by pouring it on ice and hydrochloric acid (glacial acetic acid in case of esters of nicotinic acid and isonicotinic acid). The yellow product obtained was crystallised from alcohol or a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid.

3. Preparation of 2,4-disubstituted 1,5-benzodiazepines (VI)

A mixture of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.01 mol), 1,3-dione (0.01 mol), alcohol (15 ml) and glacial acetic acid (5 ml) was heated for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and the precipitate formed was crystallised from alcohol or alcohol acetic acid mixture.

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